

Dundee DiscouRSE: Can we capture what dRTPs do?

Hi I'm James Friel, I work as a senior research software engineer at the health informatics centre here in Dundee and I have a really hard time telling people what I do.

I come from a long line of public servants, my mums a nurse and my dad was a police officer. Firefighters, teachers, the Friels have done it all.

So when great aunt kate asks at Christmas lunch "What are you doing with yourself James?", I never really have a straight answer.

Like everybody here, I wear a lot of hats – I write grant applications, give presentations, I help people fix problems, and sometimes even get to write some software.

Now don't get me wrong, I love this job, but by not coming from an academic background, the job progression is really weird.

In industry, you know the next position you're working towards, you can see the metrics on how many customers are using that new feature you've implemented. Your boss is happy if the customer is happy and you're delivering on time and under budget. You have a lane and you stick to it.

Research is weird, we're all funded a bit on this, a bit on that. Helping out where we can, just to keep all the plates spinning. And this can be a difficult, isolating environment for those that aren't on an academic track, but instead support and enable the research.

This discourse network calls these people dRTPS, or digital research technical professionals. The engineers, analysts, librarians and so many more that sit alongside the researchers, making the whole thing tick along.

Now, I don't know about anyone else, but I find this type of role can be quite isolating at times, being the only technical person on a project, nobody to knock ideas around with, unsure if you're making the right decisions and how to develop for the future.

I think in the middle of one of these project isolation cycles the discourse network put out their first flexible funding call. The discourse network is a ukri funded network project with the aim of supporting the development of leaders across all dRTPs.

As it was their first round, they kept the scope very wide, but were funding 10-20 project up to £10k each for any proposal relevant to the discourse aims. The application itself didn't seem to onderous, 13 hundered words divided up into the usual approach, vision, risks etc.

I put together a submission called “Application of the direct framework across multi-disciplinary teams” or as I have been calling it the “Dundee discourse” project.

The idea behind the project is quite straightforward – there are a lot of dRTPs in Dundee doing excellent work in data engineering, output checking, software development and project management – but a lot of them are silod off, working in one domain or another, unaware if there is anyone else working on similar stuff to them, or if something like what they’re doing has been done before.

So that raises the questions:

- What am I doing? What skills am I utilising?
- Has anyone walked this path before?

To answer that first question, “what skills am I using”, the discourse network has put a lot of effort into developing the DIRECT framework, it’s a tool to help classify and describe the wide range of technical and non technical skills dRTPs use.

As part of the Dundee discourse project we’re taking this framework and putting it through the wringer to see how well it covers the dRTP skillset, and identify what is missing.

We’re doing this by asking dRTP participants in Dundee to complete the direct framework self-assessment and nominating a colleague of theirs to also complete the assessment about the participants skills.

Now I think it’s widely accepted that we will underrate ourselves compared to how others would rate us. So it will be interesting to see the discrepancy in self vs colleague direct-framework assessments. While we won’t be able to share individual results, we’re hoping that the overall aggregate results will prove empowering for the participants.

Along with completing the direct framework, we’ve developed a feedback questionnaire to capture participants thoughts around the framework as it stands, their experiences as a dRTP, and their thoughts on any skills or abilities that they feel are not captured in the self-assessment framework.

We’re running this portion of the project until the end of April, so if you know a dRTP in Dundee, please encourage them to get involved.

I think the second question we raised, “Has anyone walked this path before?” is even more important for unifying the dRTP community. As a part of the Dundee discourse project we’re going to look at participants responses to identify skill overlaps, upskilling opportunities, and potential career progressions within the cohort.

With participants consent, we want to facilitate networking opportunities between dRTPs where there may be collaboration or learning opportunities.

Along with this, we are looking to bring more visibility to the dRTP network within Dundee. The project has been funded to host a number of collaboration and networking events, because who doesn't love a free lunch. Through these events we're hoping to foster a strong dRTP community within Dundee and build a supporting, inclusive community for the long term.

We're looking to wrap the project up by Halloween, so I'll hopefully have some results to share with you all then. But all going well, we would be interested in a follow-on project to expand Scotland wide, so if anyone would be interested in supporting this, please do get in touch.

To conclude, being a DRTP is weird, and I still don't know what to tell my great aunt at Christmas.

But the discourse network is doing great work to support the development of dRTPs, their next funding call is in Spring, and I would encourage everyone to apply if they have an idea.

It's still early days for the Dundee discourse project, but we have received a lot of support the discourse network, the university, and other dRTPS, and are looking forward to running the project.

Thank you,

Any questions?